

Electrical Conductance of Sodium Diethyldithiocarbamate in Water

A. M. Trivedi, K. P. Soni*, and I. M. Bhatt

From our earlier studies^{1,2} on the reagent, sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (NaDDTC), it was concluded that the corresponding acid was a dibasic one. In the present communication physical properties of diethyldithiocarbamate ion have been investigated with the conclusion that NaDDTC is a uni-univalent salt. The ionic conductance of the DDTC ion has been determined for the first time as well as its energy of activation. The value determined is of the order of the ionic conductance of other organic ions.

Procedure.—Stock solutions of the salt of the molarities 0.05 and 0.04 were prepared and the required solutions were obtained by suitable dilutions with water. The temperatures $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$ were maintained by an automatic thermoregulator. Conductivity water (sp. conductance 3.0×10^{-6} mhos/cm) was used throughout. The Leeds and Northrup assembly was employed for the measurement of conductance. The results obtained are represented in Fig. 1 and 2.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Hydrolysis of sodium diethyldithiocarbamate would result in the formation of a strong base, sodium hydroxide, and a weak acid, dithiocarbamic acid. The hydrolysis was observed to be a slow process and since measurements were made as soon as possible after dilution, the increase in conductance due to hydrolysis might be neglected. In fact, the calculations showed that the contribution to specific conductance due to hydrolysis was not greater than 0.3% of the measured conductance of the salt.

*Present address: Chemistry Department, M. G. Science Institute, Ahmedabad-0.

1. Soni and Trivedi, *this Journal*, 1960, 37, 340; 1961, 38, 65.

2. Soni *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1966, 43, 65.

For a uni-univalent electrolyte, the Onsager equation may be written as

$$\lambda = \lambda_0 - (A + B\lambda_0)\sqrt{C}$$

where λ and λ_0 are the equivalent conductances at concentrations C and zero, respectively. The values ' A ' and ' B ', which are constant at a definite temperature, are obtained from literature³. The extrapolated values of λ_0 are 83.8 and 106.5 mhos cm^2 at 25° and 36°, respectively. The values of the slopes of the two curves (calculated from the above equation) are 78.9 and 99.5. The corresponding values, read from the graph, are 77.1 and 93.2, respectively. Hence, it may be concluded that the sodium diethyldithiocarbamate is a salt of uni-univalent type, dissociating as

The equivalent conductance of the salt at 25° is 83.8 mhos cm^2 . The ionic conductance of sodium ion⁴ at 25° being 50.11, the ionic conductance of diethyldithiocarbamate will be 33.7 mhos cm^2 at 25°.

The influence of temperature on equivalent conductance may be expressed by the approximate expression:

$$\lambda_0 t = \lambda_0^{25} [1 + \alpha(t - 25)]$$

where $\lambda_0 t$ is the equivalent conductance at infinite dilution at t° and λ_0^{25} is the corresponding value at 25°. The values of λ_0^{35} and λ_0^{25} are 106.5 and 83.8 mhos cm^2 , respectively. Substituting these values in the above expression, α turns out to be 0.027 per degree centigrade.

Since ionic conductance depends on the rate of movement, conductance may be treated in a manner analogous to other processes which increase at a definite rate on increasing the temperature. We have,

$$\lambda_0 = A e^{-E/RT}$$

' A ' may be taken as constant for a small temperature range. ' E ' is the activation energy of the process which determines the rate of movement of the ion. Differentiating the above equation with respect to temperature, we have

$$\alpha = E/RT^2 \quad (\alpha = 1/\lambda_0 \cdot \frac{d\lambda_0}{dt})$$

Substituting the value of α (temperature coefficient), ' E ' comes to be 4.8 kcal.

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CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
UNIVERSITY SCHOOL OF SCIENCE,
GUJARAT UNIVERSITY,
AHMEDABAD-9.

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3. Kortum and Bockris, "Text-book of Electrochemistry", Vol. II, 1949, p. 696, Elsevier Publishing Co., N. Y.
4. Glasstone, "Introduction to Electrochemistry", 1st ed., 1954, p. 56, D. Van Nostrand and Co., Inc. N. Y.